

Repercussions of the covid-19 pandemic on offshore work in the oil and gas industry

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Abstract: The article has as its theme the offshore work in the oil and gas industry (IO&G) in Brazil at the interface with the Covid-19 Pandemic highlighting some repercussions of this large event on working conditions and workers. Objective: To know the repercussions of the COVID-19 pandemic on the *offshore* working conditions of the oil and gas industry from the testimony of the workers. Methodology: qualitative study supported by bibliographic research and analysis of the testimonies of eight IO&G workers collected in two focus groups conducted online. Conclusions: The Covid-19 pandemic had repercussions on society in general and on the working class that has had its working conditions changed. The IO&G created protocols and guidelines for the prevention of contagion identified in the study as triggers of sadness, loneliness, anxiety, fear and feeling of loss as a result of the intensification the working day, the periods in offshore activity, the lack of information, the increased social isolation, distancing from family and social network, which generated intense suffering. Coping with large-scale events such as the Pandemic requires the creation of strategies and rapid responses by IO&G, especially regarding offshore work, can prevent processes of suffering and illness of the offshore worker and positively impacting on work activities.

Keywords: offshore work, focus group, covid-19 pandemic.

Repercussões da pandemia de covid-19 no trabalho offshore na indústria de óleo e gás

Resumo: O artigo tem como tema o trabalho *offshore* na indústria de óleo e gás (IO&G) no Brasil na interface com a Pandemia da Covid-19 destacando algumas repercussões desse evento de grande proporção nas condições de trabalho e nos trabalhadores. Objetivo: conhecer quais as repercussões da Pandemia da covid-19 nas condições de trabalho *offshore* da indústria de óleo e gás a partir do depoimento dos trabalhadores. Metodologia: estudo do tipo qualitativo amparado em pesquisa bibliográfica e análise dos depoimentos de oito trabalhadores da IO&G colhidos em dois grupos focais realizados na modalidade online. Conclusões: A Pandemia da Covid-19 repercutiu na sociedade em geral e, em especial na classe trabalhadora que teve suas condições de trabalho alteradas. A IO&G criou protocolos e orientações para prevenção do contágio identificados no estudo como desencadeadores de tristeza, solidão, ansiedade, medo e sensação de prejuízo resultado da ampliação da jornada de trabalho, dos períodos na atividade offshore, da insuficiência de informações, do aumento do isolamento social, do afastamento da família e da rede social o que gerou intenso sofrimento. O enfrentamento de eventos de grande proporção como a Pandemia impõe a criação de estratégias e respostas rápidas pela IO&G em especial no que se refere ao trabalho offshore, o que pode prevenir processos de sofrimento e adoecimento do trabalhador offshore impactando positivamente nas atividades laborais.

Palavras-chave: Trabalho offshore, grupo focal, pandemia covid-19.

1. Introduction

The Oil and Gas Industry (IO&G) is a complex organization identified by the high degree of technology, highly specialized structures and specific characteristics of the type of work performed (Milani et al., 2007). These specific characteristics of the type of work are crossed with uncertainties, which makes predictability a challenge and decision-making an arduous and unwarranted task.

Made under the institutional project: "Integration of Human Factors and Resilience to Strengthen a Culture of Safety in the Oil and Gas Industry" - Human Factors/HF, this article proposes some reflections on work in a complex socio-technical system, in this case the oil and gas industry (O&G) in Brazil, in particular the offshore activity and the fight against the Covid-19 Pandemic, as a large-scale event that brought about an adverse context with material risk of death and important sequelae to those who were infected.

The aforementioned institutional project is carried out in partnership between the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul - PUCRS - and the Libra Consortium, which studies the relationship between human factors and safety culture in the Brazilian IO&G with the objective of building knowledge and propose alternatives that have a positive impact on safety management.

The study presented here is an excerpt from the project coordinated by the team of Social Workers researchers, whose period is restricted to the Covid-19 Pandemic, the collection instrument is an online focus group and whose focus of analysis is the repercussions of the pandemic on work and on workers in the IO&G.

The contributions of this article regarding the repercussions of the Pandemic on offshore working conditions suggest that IO&G empowers leaders and workers to promote and socialize actions and strategies that focus on educational processes, of sensibilization, listening and information with attention to internal networks and those of community and family support and support. These are actions and strategies that can contribute to prevent and/or mitigate repercussions such as: physical exhaustion due to the intensification of work, feelings of lack of protection and neglect, feelings of loss and difficulty in adapting and accepting new orientations and protocols, anxiety about the risk of illness, feelings of sadness, loneliness, anxiety, fear and dissatisfaction due to social isolation and decreased socializing with family and social network by the changes in working hours.

Based on the analyses and reflections presented, we intend to provide the bases for other studies that can strengthen an increasingly urgent demand: the confrontation of large-scale events and adverse contexts by complex socio-technical organizations.

2. Oil and gas industry in Brazil and the covid-19 pandemic

Brazil is blessed "*by God and beautiful by nature*", an inspiring source for different forms of art. Its flora, fauna, savannah, mountains and sea inspire music, poetry, literature and cinema. This nature has also favoured the Brazilian IO&G, placing the country in second place in South America in terms of proven oil reserves, only behind Venezuela (Sholvin et al., 2020).

These production records are reported in the Brazilian Statistical Yearbook of Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels (2021, p.5), which informs that the national oil production in 2020 grew 5.7%, reaching a volume of 2.9 million barrels per day. This significant increase in production is related to the supply of pre-salt oil, which reached the highest value in the historical series of oil exports, with an increase of 1.4 million barrels per day.

In addition to the importance of this industry as a producer of goods and services, the discussion presented here addresses its complexity due to the use of highly sophisticated technology and the characteristics of the work performed, especially offshore work, which involves specific singularities and risks. The O&G industry activities are described as “a large process, composed of six activities, from ‘the well to the gas station’: exploration, development, production, refining, transport and distribution” (Milani et al., 2020, p.9), or divided into 3 sectors:

downstream, midstream e upstream. The latter sector includes the search for oil and gas fields, and the drilling and operation of wells. The midstream sector encompasses the transport, storage and wholesale of raw or purified and refined products. The downstream sector comprises both the refinement of crude oil and the purification of natural gas as extracted, as well as the sale and distribution of oil and gas products (Sholvin et al, 2020, p.86).

Based on this description, it is possible to state the complexity of this socio-technical system, considering: high competitiveness, control and organization of all the structures involved, pressure for deadlines, transparency requirements, demand for fluid communication and information standards that affect the decision making and that can “incubate accidents” (Dekker & Pruchnicki, 2014). The complexity of a system impacts both the possibilities of change and the reverberations of the changes made, because even when such changes are small and isolated, they lead to unpredictable consequences and in different places (Dekker & Pruchnicki, 2014).

This context of high complexity was impacted, from March 2020, by a pandemic that lead to health measures that imposed restrictions on population mobility due to the high infectiousness of the Coronavirus (Covid-19) and its lethal risk. The covid-19 Pandemic has brought significant changes to the dynamics of the world economy and the world of work, it has collapsed health systems, profoundly changed mobility and the coexistence between people, demanding the isolation of the population.

The Brazilian Unified Health System (SUS), already deteriorated, was stretched at all levels with a higher impact at the tertiary level, with hospitals reaching occupancy rates above 100% on numerous occasions. When demanded far beyond the possibilities of the health network equipment, health professionals were particularly hit by the demands of the work, to which they paid with their health and even with their lives. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that 80,000 to 180,000 health professionals died between January 2020 and May 2021 due to Covid-19¹ (WHO, 2021).

In different scopes, the consequences and changes brought about by the pandemic caused important changes in the world of work, and the working class was impacted in different ways by the necessary adaptations to reduce the risk of contamination, prevent illness and prevent the death of workers and their families. In addition to other consequences, such as: unemployment of a significant portion of the population; reduction in working hours; overload and insecurity regarding the continuity of activities; readjustment of work activities to the remote model and readjustments of work practices for the segments that kept face-to-face activities.

¹ The WHO and its partners stated that in addition to the great concern over deaths, an increasing proportion of the workforce continues to suffer from burnout, stress, anxiety and fatigue. They called on responsible leaders and politicians to ensure fair access to vaccines so that health professionals are prioritized. <https://brasil.un.org/pt-br/152760-ate-180-mil-profissionais-de-saude-morreram-de-covid-19-informa-oms>, captured on Dec 4, 2021

Some sectors, in different countries, were immediately hit with irreversible losses, such as the leisure, culture and health sectors

[...] the Coronavirus has affected numerous strata of human life: economy, politics, industry, business, transport, health, social, income, the job market, and many others. Besides the scars and trails of fatalities left behind by the COVID-19, business as a whole has suffered immense losses as a consequence of both the national and international travel ban. Of special note is the impact experienced by the Travel and Tourism (T&T) sector which to a large extent remains the major economic booster of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of numerous countries" (Masoga, 2020, p.2).

To deepen knowledge about the impacts of the pandemic, there was a profusion of research, articles and publications with a focus mainly on activities related to the health area. It is known that the intensification of work with the vulnerable population exposed workers to contagion not only in the health area (Botão & Nunes, 2020; Rueda, 2020 *apud* Dums & Silva, 2022).

Santos et al. (2020) in a review of the literature on covid-19 and workers' health, analysed scientific productions with emphasis on those works not related to the health sector. The occupations indicated in the articles were organized into five groups: "health area (22%), transport drivers (18%), service workers and salespeople (18%), cleaning staff, domestic workers (9%) and public security workers (7%)" (2020, p.3). For the authors, the findings "evidence the permanent invisibility of essential workers such as urban cleaners, maids, delivery men, motorcycle boys, supermarket cashiers, workers in the fuel industry, the chemical industry producing raw materials for sanitizers and medicines, among others" (2020, p.3). The study included reports from international agencies in which 82.3% of the publications addressed the situation of health workers at the interface with Covid-19 with less than 20% going to workers in other sectors. Even among the groups cited as invisible by Santos, there are no workers in offshore activities, which reiterates the importance of this study.

To cope with the pandemic, the Brazilian Institute of Petroleum, Gas and Biofuels (IBP), with the objective of reducing the impact of the pandemic, prepared a booklet for responsible operation in the offshore segment during the Covid-19 pandemic, recommending strategies and guidelines for actions to be carried out at pre-embarkation, embarkation and disembarkation of the workers.

The booklet guidelines are summarized below:

» Pre-embarkation instructions on quarantine, modes of transport and movement, embarkation and pre-embarkation screening: - mandatory quarantine for all workers at pre-embarkation to monitor health conditions; - information on the risk classification for Covid-19; - instructions on care and monitoring of the health area of organizations; - information on the quarantine spent at a worker' home or in a hotel intended for workers and on travel by land, water and air transport; instructions at pre-embarkation screening regarding physical facilities at airports and ports; symptom check and testing for Covid-19 via rapid test (IgG/IgM) or RT-PCR (Reverse Transcription – Polymerase Chain Reaction).

» At embarkation, in order to control and reduce exposure to contamination and considering the confinement on platforms, the measures and actions to be taken are the following: - - focusing on cleaning and sanitizing the high-risk areas; - access control for visitors; - emphasis on personal hygiene, social distancing, use of masks; - no sharing of food, personal items, etc.; - organization of procedures on rotating teams and working

hours; -specific care and attention for handling cargo; -adjustments in working hours and practices, avoiding crowding at meetings and meals; -provisioning and orienting the use of PPE and safety training and guidance.

» At disembarkation, the instructions for monitoring the health of offshore workers are repeated.

Surrounded by multiple factors and contexts, the Coronavirus found fertile ground to spread among the lack of protection, low immunity, unpreparedness of the population regarding the forms of contagion and prevention and in the lack of knowledge about its aggressiveness. These factors were increased by the indolence and irresponsibility of those in office, who invested little in protective equipment, delayed tests, were reluctant to manufacture and apply vaccines and advertised treatments proven to be ineffective.

Uncertainties regarding the trajectory of the pandemic and the general level of anxiety and distress borne by populations increased the pressure on health and well-being systems in different countries (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020).

The restrictions and readjustments necessary to contain the spread of the disease had and still have repercussions on the work condition of various organizational systems and, consequently, on the lives of workers in these systems/organizations. The IO&G in particular, due to the specific configuration of on-board work, faced several factors (external and internal) which, amplified by the devastating effects of the pandemic, impacted the emotional and social conditions of workers and, obviously, the safety processes.

Offshore work presents important differences compared to other types of work. It is work that is carried out in a closed system that involves constant risk, specific forms of control of time and space with control of the worker's life, rotating work, organized in isolation, with periods of absence of the worker from the domestic space and family life, such as impediments or limitations to the participation of the worker in family events and rituals (births, baptisms, growth of children, marriages, graduations,) has repercussions on the convivial repercussion the affective and social relationships and may trigger serious consequences the health of the worker at the mental, social, physical level and affect the performance of tasks and increasing the risk of occupational accidents (Antoniolli et al., 2015; Coelho et al. 2018, Leite, 2021; Silva et al., 2007).

3. Methodology

The project, which supports this article, was approved in the period before the pandemic with the aim of identifying the perceptions, beliefs, feelings, meanings, ideas and attitudes of offshore workers about offshore work and safety culture. With the occurrence of the Pandemic the objectives were expanded, including the repercussions in working conditions. The execution took place in 2020 adjusting the health protocol guidelines. This is a qualitative study, with bibliographic research and analysis of the testimonies of participants collected through the Focus Group (FG) instrument.

The Focus Group approach was chosen because it is characterized as an informal discussion group, of small size, whose purpose is to obtain qualitative and in-depth information on certain topics, which are the focus of the discussion, based on the perceptions of the participants. The material for analysis comprises both spoken content and non-verbal communication, movements, reactions and mobilizations among the participants. In addition to questions and answers, the interactions and sharing that take place during the meeting are important, and can provide new elaborations of opinions and

perceptions (Duarte, 2007; Morgan, 1997), because they show “a range of data (produced by the interaction) that reveal points of consensus and dissent, fundamental to answer the research questions (Abreu et al., 2009, p.8)

In the study, the FG was conducted online in October and December 2020. And the team of researchers also carried out a theoretical densification on this modality of execution of the FG, finding an insufficient scientific production that, with the advent of the pandemic, should be expanded. Some limits and possibilities observed in the online modality were: challenge of performing an activity dependent on the oscillation of technology (Internet); interspersed or interrupted communication; limitation in the observation of non-verbal communication, movements, reactions and mobilizations among the participants; difficulty in using dynamics of integration and facilitation of participation; difficulty in monitoring participation via chat and option of some participants for keeping the camera closed (by oscillation of the system, by lack of conditions in the equipment or by choice).

In conducting the methodology, the following steps were: 1. The bibliographic research focused on the following topics: online focus group, covid-19 pandemic, socio-technical systems and offshore work; 2) Selection of the sample of no more than 12 participants indicated by the organization meeting the criteria of work in the oil and gas industry in offshore activities, diversity as to age, time working in the organization, acting in different activities, functions and responsibilities, 3) Invitation sent to the participants by email informing in detail the objective of the research, the online modality, the voluntariness, anonymity, right of withdrawal, duration of the meeting and the form of collection, meeting the recommendations of research ethics. The exclusion criteria included workers who perform their activities on land (*onshore*), 4). Definition of the virtual platform used, 5). Elaboration of the GF roadmap, 6) Commitment to the confidentiality of the information provided, 7). Term of Free and Informed Consent, 8) Realization of the FGs, 9) Transcription and analysis of the results, 10) Preparation of technical reports and scientific articles.

There were 2 FGs in which 8 workers participated, 4 in each group, all male, aged between 30 and 45 years, with different times of connection to the oil and gas industry, all working at the operational level but with different functions in the three platforms belonging to the Libra Consortium. This small sample is representative of the set of workers in the offshore activity of the organizations surveyed: most are men, married, aged between 30 and 50 years, high school or higher education level, with ties to the organizations over 5 years.

The meetings took place through the Microsoft *Teams* platform, in time and shift for realization included Sunday and Saturday afternoon meeting the convenience and suggestion of the participants with approximately two hours of duration. The Free and Informed Consent Term (FICT) was read and recorded with the consent of the participants at the beginning of the meetings. The instruments and consent process used in the present study were approved as an amendment to the umbrella project under CAAE 30745920.3.0000.5336.

The FGs were conducted by two researchers, from the area of Social Work, members of the Human Factor (HF) project that used a script composed of the generating themes: participation, working relationships with the team and internal support network, health conditions, meaning and satisfaction at work, safety culture, autonomy/decision-making, culture and external support network. The themes were shared on the computer

screen so that each participant could point out the one that most interested them and share with the group the reason for the choice and the association with offshore work and safety at work. The coordination ensured and stimulated the participation of the entire group, which allowed to study the social and psychosocial aspects related to the safety culture, observe the interaction and know the opinions and experiences of *offshore* workers in relation to the pandemic.

In this article, the participants are identified by an alphanumeric system to preserve their identity, their talks are fully transcribed and the data produced are analysed and interpreted through content analysis. The focus of the article is on the working conditions impacted by the pandemic.

4. Results and Discussions

It is known that offshore work is carried out in a complex socio-technical system, reliant on high technology, with demands for responsibilities that depend on individual and collective actions, transparent communication and decision-making, and other factors which present both a risk of loss of life and incalculable financial losses.

The feeling of permanent risk, constant uncertainty and the assumption that individual or collective actions can cause disasters justify specific forms of control. Furthermore, on-board work results in periods away from family life, making it impossible to be present in family rituals and participate in important decisions with the family. These characteristics single out a type of work that can trigger anxiety, fear, sadness, loneliness, feelings that found in the Pandemic a fertile ground for exacerbation, with visible illness processes, manifested in the narratives shared by the workers in the focus groups.

Difficulties in adapting and accepting the new protocols adopted by the organizations due to the pandemic were identified, even though the necessity of guidelines was recognized. The change in the organization of the workday to meet the health protection and monitoring actions was presented with unanimous dissatisfaction among the participants. Dissatisfaction with the increased number of days on-board stands out, with less time spent with the family and a more tiring journey, "it is very hard, it is not easy, staying there for 28 days [...] waking up early in the morning, is very hard" (Participant 1). The 14-day journey on board and 14 days on land was changed, the requirement of quarantine in a hotel extended the isolation and the period away from family, the displacements from one state to another exposed the workers to the risks of contagion:

"[...] our regular work schedule is 14 by 14, it's two weeks onboard and two at home. But, because of this pandemic period, the load has doubled, so 28. That's twice the time staying onboard. Now they stay twice as long and coworkers who live in other states, embark in different states, need to travel by plane. Then you need to quarantine at the hotel, which to me is one of the worst things" (Participant 2).

The feeling of danger and the fear of contagion accompany all the reports. According to the participants, workers residing out of the state of embarkation spend the pre-embarkation quarantine (7 days) at a hotel paid by the company, while residents of the state quarantine, that is, in family life. This new protocol was found to enhance the feelings of loss and the reasons mentioned above, such as, social isolation, separation from the family and social network compound with the negative comparison with co-workers who quarantine at their homes. In addition, the fact that the period spent in quarantine is deducted from the days off with the family contributes to this dissatisfaction.

And why is it not the other way around? Why instead of staying 21 at home, you stay 28 “[...], being 28 at home, and the 7 days of quarantine on your working schedule, not on your days off. Got it?” (Participant 3).

The feeling of harm exacerbated by the verification of the different implementation of the protocol among the workers and by the feeling of lack of protection and neglect of the company: “*And whenever we bring something to the company, the company doesn't care, really, that's the truth*” (participant 4). Although the worker recognizes the importance of his work: “*because if you are imbued with that grit, you have to keep going! Because if the ship stops, it's not good, not for us, not for anyone. It's our job*” (Participant 2), and if you make an effort to do it even in adverse conditions, the feeling is that there is no recognition by the company and that the information provided about the pandemic is insufficient:

“Alright, we are going through a difficult time, we are helping the company, but we are not being helped. [...] the question that remains is, when, until when are we going to live in this modality? How long are we going to work this way? Having no one that says the following: [- name mentioned by the participant omitted] - in January, or in July..., we are going to get the vaccine and that will soon be over. But nobody says anything” (Participant 5).

Considering that vaccination in Brazil started on January 17, 2021, and was initially destined for priority groups – health workers, people living in long-stay institutions aged 60 years or older, people with disabilities admitted at institutions, and the indigenous population living in villages – vaccination of offshore workers was not included in the vaccination schedule in Phase 1, thus some information was not known during the collection period and, therefore, could not be transmitted by the organization. However, in addition to concrete information, the feeling expressed by the worker is one of non-reciprocity, which fosters a work environment that lacks empathy.

Similar analyses are present in the study conducted by Vinagre et al. (2022) with the objective of investigating changes in the management of offshore work caused by the covid-19 pandemic was observed process of weakening of the previously more integrated work teams due to the changes caused by the measures of protection and prevention of contagion. The study points out that the changes in offshore working conditions were perceived by workers as those who suffered “greater embarrassment than the vast majority of the population” (2022, p.15), because they did not enjoy like other workers “the feeling of coming home and taking off the mask” (p.15) since they did not return to their domestic spaces remaining confined. The offshore routine required by the new protocols of the oil and gas industry was lived with much suffering by the workers.

In this perspective, Noal et al. (2020) in the “Recomendações e Orientações em Saúde Mental e Atenção Psicossocial na Covid-19” (Recommendations and Guidelines for Mental Health and Psychosocial Care for Covid-19), published by FIOCRUZ, estimates that a third to 50% of a population exposed to an epidemic. In the testimonies of the participants, the perplexity, the global risk, the feeling of annihilation, the unpredictability and scarcity of information, confinement and the prospect of real risk of contagion and death are recipes for the development of anxiety processes and other often disabling feelings:

“It's like this, very quiet. And we are in this moment. There are people, people who are calm, just like me or [the name mentioned by the participant is omitted] ... until the day we go there (embarkation). You see the degree of anxiety that we are experiencing. Something I never had, anxiety. I need to know what's going to

happen, I don't understand anything, got it? So, this is a very important thing to bring up for our moment. If it is difficult, for us it is even more so" (Participant 5).

Regarding these feelings, Noal et al. (2020) state that "during a pandemic, it is expected that people will often be on alert, worried, confused, stressed and feeling a lack of control facing the uncertainties of the moment" (p.21). By restricting spaces and moments of socialization, the health measures have switched on the state of alertness, which has implications for mental health and quality of the work life. Processes of suffering and illness were unleashed as the pandemic increasingly restricted mobility and increased isolation. In offshore work, these processes were intensified due to the limits imposed by the distance, the impossibility of going ashore immediately, the worsening of the health situation and the interaction with suffering colleagues. The testimonies reveal experiences of emotional illness aggravated by confinement in hotel rooms or by the extension of the period embarked:

"[...] the guy (another worker), calling for mommy. Mother, mommy. And leaving behaving like crazy. A guy saw him, and he was saying he was an animal. Another (worker), for example, who [I] was looking yesterday, just yesterday. I think you may have already seen - the name mentioned by the participant was omitted -, a boy who was left abandoned, caught Covid on board, was abandoned in a hotel, after two days the system told him the following: - "Now you are on your own". Since he caught on board, he should have received treatment before being taken to his family. Imagine you, catching a disease on board and taking it to your family, contaminating everyone. Who will be responsible for this?" (Participant 5).

It is true that the pandemic is leaving its marks on all populations, disorganizing collective and individual ways of living everyday life, reaching all spaces and life in infinitesimal units. However, it is also true that these marks have unequal proportions and are not expressed in a homogeneous way. Repeating the finding - which has become commonplace and which makes sense in the O&G industry -, that the pandemic left everyone in the same ocean, but not in the same boat, because even though the Pandemic has a collective character, social inequalities allow more or less protection to be had depending on the economic condition and access to resources by each segment. According to Dimenstein et al. (2020),

"In this new universe in which we find it difficult to recognize ourselves, life scenarios will directly impact the experiences of suffering, will favor or not the elaboration of ways of confronting it, individual and collective, to address the imponderable helplessness, with the subjective emptying and with the effects of the policies of abandonment and death that subject vulnerable portions of the population to violent daily catastrophes – now widely exposed" (p.5).

The ways of confrontation are given in the individual possibilities and not in more collective measures, penalizing and overloading the worker even more:

"[...] but I can say that it is already starting to affect me psychologically. I already started, I already had, I had been in therapy for over 5 years, I stopped, and I came back 4 months ago because I was already in a ... chaotic state, you know? I didn't even want to come to work anymore" (Participant 6).

The warnings regarding the pandemic context prolong suffering, sadness, death fantasies, fear and anxiety, requiring measures and care to prevent medium and long-term consequences, avoiding risks such as that of medicalization - *"look (participant shows*

medication blisters), to be in a good mood. So as not to grab anyone by the neck on board” (Participant 7) -, and the worsening of illness processes.

The urgent need for increased attention by organizations to other demands from workers stands out, as well as the promotion of actions more focused on aspects mainly related to the mental health of workers. The Center for Studies and Research in Health Emergencies and Disasters (CEPEDES), of Fiocruz (Melo et al., 2020), in the Table Suggestions for care and recommendations to managers for Mental Health and Psychosocial Care actions (Melo et al., 2020, p.29) pointed out several recommendations during the Pandemic aimed at the general population, for densification in this study, the authors adapted the original Framework by inserting recommendations that contemplate offshore work and the different phases of the pandemic (Table 1).

Table 1 - Recommendations for addressing and protecting workers regarding the pandemic

Phases of the pandemic and the impacts on offshore workers	Recommendations
Aspects for first approach	General initial recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sense of inevitability with a high level of stress in the population; - Exacerbated pre-existing positive/negative human characteristics; - Anxiety, stress, insecurity and obsessive surveillance of the symptoms of the disease. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socialize educational information about the forms of contagion; - Recruit and train teams experienced in psychosocial care and mental health; - Prepare emotional/psychological support groups, aided by Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), for when the workers are disembarked; - Identify vulnerable groups from a psychosocial perspective; - Map out the Institutions and social actors to provide networked psychosocial care;
Intensification of negative feelings	Recommendations for the duration of the pandemic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear, feelings of loneliness and vulnerability; - State of lethargy or disordered agitation; - Difficulty to adapt to changes in habitual life patterns: restrictions of movement, mask use, reduction of direct physical contact, closing of schools, churches, services, etc.; - Emotional and panic crises, collective reactions of agitation, loss of control of pre-existing psychic disorders, psychosomatic disorders; - Suicide attempts, difficulty to mourn; - Work overload of workers in relation to family members (elderly parents, small children, spouses, etc.) - Stigmatization of people suspected and confirmed positive for COVID-19; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness, inform and provide health care resources; - Promote the rapid assessment of workers' psychosocial needs; - Support the fundamental actions of early detection, care, and identification of the most recurrent acute psychosocial suffering; - Inform and instruct on: what is happening, actions taken and what people should do; - Ensure that workers' needs are met to face the pandemic, such as: protection, family life, access to health care resources, promotion of dignity and guarantee of livelihood; - Offer psychosocial support and care (face-to-face or online), observing the urgency and biosafety regulations, according to different groups and demands; - Develop mechanisms of care among peers, families, their socio-affective networks and community support; - Promote individual and collective professional self-care strategies; - Outreach and offer psychosocial care in case of emergency, such as: psychotic crisis, suicide attempts, among others; - Offer specialized services aimed at the specific care of infected people; - Ensure networked psychosocial support is available for safe funerals and care for families in mourning.

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Permanence of negative post-pandemic feelings	Post-pandemic recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear of a new pandemic; - Depression, pathological grief, post-traumatic stress disorder, alcohol and drug abuse, violent behaviour, among others; - Difficulty in resuming work routines and activities; - Reframing of life projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investing in qualified social communication strategies that promote collective relationships, solidarity and empathy among workers, aiming at the development of health and safety processes; - Strengthening the organization's actions and projects that promote life, professional self-care, community, caring for the mental health of workers and their families; - Monitor, evaluate and share the experiences and lessons learned.

Source: Adapted from the Suggestion of Care Chart and recommendations to managers on Mental Health and Psychosocial Care actions (Melo et al., 2020, p.29).

5. Conclusions and contributions

The Covid-19 pandemic has had repercussions on society in general and especially on the working class who have had their working conditions changed. The fight against the Covid-19 Pandemic, with its contours of humanitarian crisis, imposed urgent and infinitesimal changes to the organization of life and work.

The pandemic is global, however, it has impacted life in society in different ways and intensities, and inequalities of access to the possibilities of protection have erupted, leaving no doubt about the existing social divide. The evidence of the lethality of the virus, the daily news reports on the thousands of lives lost and the concrete fear of death required the organization of a set of actions to meet the demands related to work conditions and health needs, especially for the mental and emotional health of workers.

The repercussions directly impacted the IO&G having significant effects on work conditions, especially in offshore operations, being created protocols and guidelines for the prevention of contagion identified by the study participants as triggers of sadness, anxiety, fear, loneliness, dissatisfaction and feeling of loss results of the intensification of the working day, the periods in the offshore activity, the insufficiency of information, the increase in social isolation, the distance from the family and the social network, which generated intense suffering and also risks in work activities.

The Covid-19 Pandemic has alerted us that complex socio-technical organizations, such as the O&G industry must be prepared to respond to large-scale events that create adverse contexts. Other large-scale events can (and will) occur, and the organizations must be prepared, with quick responses and qualified strategies in order to implement health and safety processes.

Coping with large-scale events such as the Pandemic requires the creation of strategies and rapid responses by IO&G, especially with regard to offshore work. As a strategy that can contribute in labour contexts such as offshore work, and considering that this pandemic was not the first and will not be the last pandemic, it is suggested that IO&G has structured an organic system for communication and crisis coping (Wu, Connors & Everly, 2020), which would involve training workers and especially leaders to promote and socialize actions educational, information about the resources of the organization and/or the network for health care; promotion of individual and collective strategies of professional self-care; provision of spaces for support/listening and psychosocial attention to different groups; encouraging mechanisms of peer care, socio-affective networks,

community and family support, creation of qualified social communication actions and mechanisms to strengthen collective relations and empathy among workers.

These actions and strategies can contribute to prevent and/or mitigate repercussions such as: physical exhaustion due to the intensification of work, feelings of lack of protection and neglect, feelings of loss and difficulty in adapting and accepting new orientations and protocols defined by the organizations, anxiety about the risks and illness, feeling of sadness, loneliness and dissatisfaction caused by changes in working conditions, which in the case of offshore work means greater social isolation and decreased interaction with family and social network (Wu, Connors & Everly, 2020).

The receipt of information and greater knowledge about reality and collective organization can reduce workers' anxiety and increase autonomy in relation to care and protection in the face of large events.

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7. References

- Abreu, N.R., Baldanza, R.F., & Gondim, S.M.G. (2009). Os grupos focais on-line: das reflexões conceituais à aplicação em ambiente virtual. *JISTEM-Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, v. 6, p. 5-24.
- Agência Nacional do Petróleo, Gás Natural e Biocombustíveis (Brasil) (2021). Anuário estatístico brasileiro do petróleo, gás natural e biocombustíveis: 2021 / Agência Nacional do Petróleo, Gás Natural e Biocombustíveis. - Rio de Janeiro: ANP, 2008- . v. : gráf., tab. Anual. Disponível para download: <https://www.gov.br/anp> e <https://www.gov.br/anp/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes>.
- Antoniolli, S.A.C., Emmel, S.V., Ferreira, G.E., Paz, P. O., & Kaiser, D.E. (2015). Trabalho offshore ea atuação do enfermeiro embarcado: uma revisão integrativa. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*, 49(4), 689-698. DOI: 10.1590/S0080-62342015000040002
- Botão, M. & Nunes, N.R. (2020). A relevância do trabalho dos assistentes sociais no enfrentamento à pandemia da COVID-19. In: A. Lole, I. Stampa, & R. L. R. Gomes, *Para além da quarentena: reflexões sobre crise e pandemia Rio de Janeiro*, Mórula, Recurso eletrônico.
- Centers For Disease Control And Prevention (2020). *How coronavirus spreads*. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/prepare/transmission.html>.
- Coelho, E.M., Amaral, O., Pereira, C., Veiga, N., Costa, J., Nelas, P., Chaves, C., & Coutinho, E. (2018). Estilos de vida em trabalhadores offshore de uma plataforma da África subsaariana. *International Journal of Developmental and Educational Psychology*, vol. 3, n. Esp.1, 299-307.
- Dekker, S. & Pruchnicki, S. (2014). Drifting into failure: theorising the dynamics of disaster incubation. *Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science*, v. 15, n. 6, p. 534-544.
- Dimenstein, M., Simoni, A.C., & Londero, M. (2020). Encruzilhadas da Democracia e da Saúde Mental em Tempos de Pandemia. *Psicologia: Ciência e Profissão*, v. 40, 2020.
- Duarte, A.B.S. (2007). Grupo focal online e offline como técnica de coleta de dados. *Inf. & Soc.:Est.*, João Pessoa, v.17, n.1, p.75-85, jan./abr.

- Dums, M. & Silva, S.C. (2022). Que Estado é Esse? desafios para o serviço social no contexto da pandemia da covid-19. In M. I. B. Bellini, F. X. Arena & J. C. Prates (org.), *Inflexões da pandemia-covid 19 na vida, nas políticas públicas e no trabalho* (pp. 485-504). Porto Alegre: ediPUCRS.
- Leite, R.M. dos S.C. (2009). Vida e trabalho na indústria de petróleo em alto mar na Bacia de Campos. *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva* [online], v. 14, n. 6, pp. 2181-2189.
- Masoga, M. (2020). The Crumbling Empire? Liberation Theological Investigation into the Impact of COVID-19 on South African Communities. *Pharos Journal of Theology*, Vol. 101.
- Melo, B., Pereira, D., Noal, D., Serpeloni, F., Kabad, J., Souza, M., & Rabelo, I. (2020). Recomendações para Gestores. In: Noal, D.; Passos, M.F; Freitas, C. (org.), *Recomendações e orientações em saúde mental e atenção psicossocial na COVID-19*. Brasília: Fundação Oswaldo Cruz.
- Milani Júnior, A., Bomtempo, J.V., & Pinto Júnior, H. (2007). A indústria do petróleo como uma organização complexa: modelagem de negócios e processo decisório. *Production*, v. 17, p. 8-32.
- Morgan, DL. (1997). *Focus groups as qualitative research*. Sage Publications.
- Noal, D.S., Passos, M.F.D., & De Freitas, C.M. (2020). *Recomendações e orientações em saúde mental e atenção psicossocial na COVID-19*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz.
- Rueda. M.F. (2020) *Os desafios cotidiano do trabalho do/da Assistente Social no âmbito dos Centros de Referência de Assistência Social*. Evento de lançamento de pesquisa do departamento de serviço social. Produção: A pesquisa a prática profissional das/os assistentes sociais frente às demandas da proteção social básica no contexto da Pandemia da COVID-19.. [S. l.: s. n.]. Disponível em: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s7Y6DdPeqO8> .
- Scholvin, S., Serra, M., Françoso, M., Bastos, P., Mello, P., & Borges, A. (2020). Densidade, distância, divisão e as redes de produção globais: o caso do setor brasileiro de petróleo e gás. *Economia e Sociedade*, 29, 85-119.
- Silva Júlio, D.I., & Ferreira, M.C. (2007). Escala para avaliação de estressores ambientais no contexto offshore oil. *Avaliação Psicológica*, 6(2), 139-146.
- Vinagre, R.F., Castro, A.C., & Alvarez, D. (2022). Algumas reflexões acerca das mudanças na gestão do trabalho offshore durante a pandemia da covid-19. *Revista Latino-Americana de Estudos Científicos – RELAEC*. v.03. n18.
- WHO - World Health Organization (2020). Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19. World Health Organization; 2020 March [Accessed 2020-11-01]. Available in: <https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020>
- Wu, A., Connors, C., & Everly, G. (2020). Covid-19: peer support and crisis Communication strategies to promote institutional resilience. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 172(12), 822–823. doi:10.7326/m20-1236.